

SHORT NOTES

THE SOLUBILITY OF LEAD MONOXIDE IN PERCHLORIC ACID AND THE FORMATION OF BASIC LEAD PERCHLORATE IN SOLUTION.

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From the study of lead iodate in perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate solution appreciable hydrolysis of Pb^{2+} to $PbOH^+$ has been observed. The first-stage hydrolysis (reaction 1) is almost complete in neutral solution (Misra and Pani, this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 387).

Out of the two well-known soluble salts of lead, the nitrate is not hydrolysed to any appreciable extent, but the acetate in dilute aqueous solution is hydrolysed to basic lead acetate. The hydrolysis in nitrate solution is probably prevented by the formation of nitrate lead complex. Acetate ion also forms complex with lead and still hydrolysis takes place, and the behaviour may be ascribed to two reasons: (i) acetic acid being a weaker acid compared to nitric acid, the salt of the former is more hydrolysed and (ii) the nitrate lead complex is probably a more stable complex than the acetate complex in aqueous solution. If the former is valid, lead perchlorate being a salt of a very strong acid is expected to be very little hydrolysed.

To verify this assumption, the solubility of lead monoxide in perchloric acid was studied. In the preparation of pure lead perchlorate Willard and Kessner have observed that a large excess of lead monoxide, over the amount required to give lead perchlorate, dissolves in perchloric acid solution (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 2402). It would be interesting to study this quantitatively. The solubility of lead monoxide in perchloric acid solution of different concentrations but of the same ionic strength was studied at 35°. G. R. quality lead monoxide was used in the investigation. The purity of the sample was further confirmed by estimating the lead content of the sample as lead sulphate. Perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate used were Analar quality reagents.

Perchloric acid of different but known concentrations containing calculated amount of sodium perchlorate to give the ionic strength 0.3 was used as solvent. Excess of lead monoxide was added and the mixture was heated to nearly 40-45° on a water-bath and placed in a thermostat at 35° for over a month. The lead contents of the filtrates were determined as sulphate (gravimetrically) and also as chromate (volumetrically). The results obtained by the two methods are in good agreement. The concentration of perchloric acid, which dissolved the lead oxide, was estimated as follows. A known volume of the filtrate was saturated with hydrogen sulphide and after complete precipitation of lead as sulphide it was filtered and hydrogen sulphide was boiled off from the filtrate. The acid present was estimated by titrating

against standard alkali. The results thus obtained are shown below. The square bracket indicates molar concentration per litre of solution. p_n of the solution was also measured.

Solvent.		Solution.		
[HClO ₄].	[NaClO ₄].	[Pb].	[HClO ₄] ₂	p_n
0.30	0.00	0.281	0.290	6.08
0.25	0.05	0.242	0.243	6.08
0.20	0.10	0.194	0.184	...
0.10	0.20	0.094	0.093	6.47

There is a slight variation in the strength of the acid originally taken [HClO₄]₁ and the strength of the acid [HClO₄]₂ obtained after precipitation of lead as sulphide. This is probably due to a slight change in volume caused by mixing of solutions of sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid. The results, however, definitely indicate the presence of lead and perchlorate in the solution in the ratio 1 : 1. The solution is very nearly neutral; the solid phase though white in colour is free from perchlorate, as indicated by drying a sample at 120° and analysing for its lead content. The dry solid is lead monoxide. The white solid in equilibrium with the solution is most probably hydrated lead oxide or lead hydroxide. The reaction may be represented by equation (2), assuming perchlorate ion to have no capacity to form complex.

In neutral solution and in absence of complex-forming ligands, lead exists as PbOH⁺ in aqueous solution. Lead monoxide behaves as a strong mono-acidic base.

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